

THE USE OF INNOVATIONAL TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING THE TOPIC EMOTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF INDIVIDUALITY

Muratova Shoista

SamSMU Pedagogical-Psychology Department Associate Professor, P.h.D.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10655077>

Abstract. *This article focuses on teaching psychology using pedagogical technologies, strengthening students' practical and theoretical knowledge of psychology through these interactive methods, and teaching them to think logically, critically, and creatively with the use of these methods.*

Keywords: *interactive methods, cluster, interview, blitz-game boomerang, teacher personality, "3x4" technology, teaching to use literature independently.*

The work of radical reform of the educational system in our country, raising it to the level of modern requirements, raising a harmonious generation for the future has become a dominant direction of State Policy.

On February 7, 2017, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "on the strategy of action" on the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan was signed.

The action strategy is carried out in five stages, each of which provides for the approval of a separate one-year state program, depending on the name of the year.

In the organization of educational and educational processes of higher educational institutions, the following: educational legislation, sub-legislative acts are used, including such organizational legal acts as decrees, decisions and orders.

The achievement of our goals in front of us depends on the construction of a new democratic society, what intellectual forces we have, what cultural and professional level our young people have achieved, what ideas they believe in, how rich they are spiritually. Therefore, it is one of our most important tasks to raise a new generation capable of expanding the possibility of moral learning, realizing the idea of national revival.

So, the main criterion for raising a harmonious generation that lays the cornerstone of our society is the ability of young people to think independently, to apply the knowledge and experience learned to practice.

The introduction of interactive teaching methods into the educational system is one of the important factors in the training of modern personnel. The most optimal way to improve the effectiveness of education in today's fast-paced times is to organize classes using interactive methods. The first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted the significance of the work in this regard: "we have declared perfect human education to be the dominant sphere of Public Policy. By a perfect person, we understand, first of all, educated people with a high consciousness, who can think independently, who will be an example to others with their behavior."

It is necessary to prohibit education one of the most complex types of human cognitive activity, greatly accelerating the development of the individual psyche and the assimilation of knowledge. In this regard, our countryman Sh.M.Mirziyoyev- " the teacher in the educational

process is not limited only to giving knowledge, but also affects the student-student in this process. This further activates their learning. As a result, the student becomes an active participant in the educational process. Achievements in education, above all, depend on the teacher.”

So, bringing innovations to the educational system, making the most of modern pedagogical Technologies, is one of the important tasks set before today's education.

In fact, interactive methods increase the productivity of the educational process, form the process of independent fixation of students, increase the enthusiasm and interest in knowledge in students, solid assimilation of knowledge, free use of them in practice, form skills and competencies.

In this regard, the head of our state notes the importance of creating a modern and rational system in the field of education, the need to update teaching methods, educational standards, textbooks and teaching aids, the use of advanced experience in knowledge, and national traditions and values in education.

Today, the application of information technology to the educational process is gaining momentum, and it is noticeable that it affects the higher quality organization of the educational process. Therefore, the application of interactive methods in the educational process, the relentless search for improving the effectiveness of Education has become an extension of today, cultivating students' reading motives.

So using a form of work aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the educational process on the basis of innovations, and not on the basis of homogeneous templates, as in traditional education, means innovation. Building on pedagogical technologies in education and striving for innovation, the use of various interactive techniques aimed at activating students will help to effectively implement the educational goal.

The appropriate, purposeful, effective use of interactive methods by teacher (educators) in the process of education and upbringing provides a wide opportunity to educate the learner (student, students) in the ability to engage in communication, engage in teamwork, logical thinking, synthesize existing ideas, analyze, find a logical connection between different views.

Innovations in turn will be associated with:

- Adoption of a new topic;
- Import new processes;
- New content of development square;
- New organizational forms of joint activities; - new management;
- Vs New Product.

For this reason, pedagogical innovation is now considered as a holistic complex process, and its interactive qualities, educational parts, functional description and continuity are being consistently researched. In this regard, if we use innovative educational technologies in the teaching of psychological sciences, it allows students to form a scientific worldview at the level of requirements established in the upgrade.

Innovation technologies are the pedagogical process and the introduction of innovations, changes in the activities of the teacher (educator) and the student, in the implementation of which mainly interactive methods are fully used. Interactive methods are collective thinking, that is, pedagogical methods of influence, which are a component of the content of Education. The peculiarity of these methods is that they are carried out only through the joint activities of the teacher (educator) and student-students.

The process of such pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, which include:

- forcing students to not be indifferent during training, to think independently, create and seek;
- to ensure that student-students have a constant interest in knowledge in the educational process;
- strengthening student-student interest in knowledge independently with a creative approach to each issue;
- development of continuous collaborative activities of teacher (educator) and student-students.

Also, in the process of teaching Economic Sciences, various technologies of innovation are used. Below are given trainings (technologies) that can be used in the training process, giving a methodological description of the procedure for conducting some of them:

The method of "networks" -aimed at teaching the student-student to think logically, expand the scope of general thought, independently use literature.

The "3x4" method is aimed at free thinking of student - students, able to give a wide range of ideas, analyze and draw conclusions in the educational process alone, in a small group, be able to give a definition. The "bliss-game" Method focuses on properly organizing action sequences, thinking logically, teaching how to choose what is needed from multiple, diverse thoughts, data based on the science you are learning.

The "interview" technique is aimed at teaching a student-student to ask, hear, answer correctly, correctly compose a question. The "hierarchy" technique aims to train them in logical, critical, creative thinking through the use of simple to complex, complex to simple transition techniques. The "boomerang" technique aims to enable students-students to work with various literature, texts during the course, outside the classroom, to memorize the material studied, to be able to speak, to articulate their mind freely, and to evaluate all student-students during one lesson. "Student" training-working with student-students in isolation is aimed at eliminating the barrier between the teacher and the student, teaching ways to work in collaboration, The training "teacher personality" is aimed at independent thinking on the topic" requirements for the teacher's personality", revealing the teacher's innovation activity, and at outlining thoughts by writing a creative essay. The technique of "communication" is aimed at attracting the attention of teachers to the audience, working cooperatively in the course of the lesson, teaching its organization. The "management" technique is aimed at introducing and teaching teachers to their methods in managing the audience as well as the methods of managing student-students in the process of work.

Fill in the " problem " organizer

Solving the problems of hacker accentuation of an individual.

Type of problem	Reasons for the origin of the problem	Ways to solve the problem and your effort
Do you think that accentuation can cause problems?		

Complete 3x4 organizer

Of the subject bazy the content of ochiba berishga Beradi and "3x4" narrowly focused applied technology of Tassasidan tirovcha, visual representation.

Fsmu technology

The technology is used to address debate issues as well as to conduct the academic process controversially, as it teaches students to defend their opinion, to think freely and pass their opinion on to others, to argue openly, and at the same time to argue culture.

A simple piece of paper distributed to the audience can express its thoughts in a clear and concise state, helping to state supporting arguments or negating points.

Φ- make your mind happy

S-give reason to your opinion Boin

M-provide proof of your stated cause

U-summarize your opinion

Group-1

Question	Does a person use mechanical memory in his daily activities?
F - please your mind	
S - give reason to your opinion Boin	
M- provide proof of your stated cause	
U - summarize your opinion	

Schedule **B/ B/ B** - I know / I want to know / I found out. Allows you to conduct research on the topic, text, section.

Develops the skills of systematic thinking, structuring, analysis.

Students:

They get acquainted with the rule for drawing up a table. Separately, in small groups, they formalize the table.

They answer the questions" What do you know about the topic "and" what do you want to know". Sections 1 and 2 of the table fill.

1. They listen to the text, read it independently.

Concepts	B	-	+
Character accentuation			
Temperament accentuation			
Individual personality characteristics			

Complete the graph b\b\b.

Text markup system

(v) - I know (-) - I want to know (+) - I found out

Rule of operation using the Insert method

1. Having read the text of the lecture, put the following signs on the edge of the text:

V-know

+ - new information for me

- - denies information I know

? - vague (requiring clarification) further information

2. Formalize the results obtained in the form of a table.

№	Topic questions	B	–	+	?

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. This book includes the speeches of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev from November 1 to November 24, 2016 at pre-election meetings with representatives of the voters of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent. /SH.M.Mirziyoyev. – Toshkent: : “O‘zbekiston”, 2017. – 488 b.
2. Ivanov I., Zufarova M. Umumiy psixologiya. z.FMJ., 2008.
3. Petrovskiy A.V. Umumiy psixologiya T; "O‘qituvchi" 1992.
4. G‘oziyev E. G‘. Umumiy psixologiya. 1-2 tom. T., Fan, 2002.
5. Davletshin M. G. Umumiy psixologiya. T., TDPU, 2002.- 218 b.
6. Xaydarov F.I., Xalilov N.I. Umumiy psixologiya T; 2009. – 242 b.12.6.
7. Muratova Sh.N. O‘smir yoshdagi o‘g‘il bolalarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlashning ijtimliy jihatlari. O‘zMU xabarlari, {1/2/1}ISSN: 2181-7324, 2020, 6-son, - B. 91-95, [19.00.00 №10]
8. Muratova Sh.N. O‘g‘il bolalarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash muammosining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari va uning o‘rganilganlik holati. O‘zMU xabarlari, {1/2/1}ISSN: 2181-7324, 9-son, - B. 82-86, [19.00.00 №10]
9. Muratova Sh.N. Otaning farzandlar tarbiyasidagi o‘rni. Ta‘lim, fan va innovasiya, ilmiy axborotnoma. 2022, 5-son, - B. 82-86, [19.00.00 №10]
10. O‘g‘il bolalarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlashning ijtimoiy-psixologik jihatlari. SamDU ilmiy axborotnoma. ISSN: 2091-54-46, 2020, 6-son (124), - B. 100-105. [19.00.00 №10].